

Energy Absorption Characterization of Composite Tubes for Railway Application

J. S. Kim, H. J. Yoon, H. S. Lee, T. S. Kwon
Railroad Structure Department, Korea Railroad Research Institute
#360-1, WolamDong, UiwangShi, GyeongGiDo, 437-757, Korea
jskim@krrri.re.kr

SUMMARY

In this study, the failure modes and energy absorption characterization of four different kinds of circular tubes made of carbon, glass, Kevlar and carbon-Kevlar hybrid fibres composites with epoxy resin have been evaluated. These tubes were fabricated with unidirectional and woven fabric tape. The woven fabric carbon/epoxy tubes absorbed more energy than others. In case of carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tubes fabricated from unidirectional tape, $[90_K/0_C]$ tubes failed in a local bucking mode and showed good post crushing integrity whereas $[90_C/0_K]$ tubes failed in a lamina bending mode and bad post crushing integrity

Keywords: Failure mode, Energy absorption, Post crushing integrity, Composite tube

1. Introductions

Weight reduction of a large structure such as a train has the advantage of the payload increase, the speed increase, and the reduction of energy consumption. The key to a successful reduction of the structural weight is to prove that the safety and performance is not compromised [1]. Recently, composite materials such as carbon/epoxy, glass/epoxy and glass/phenol are widely applied in railway field. The Korea Railroad Research Institute (KRRRI) has developed a Korean tilting train with a sandwich composite structure for bodyshell and a stainless steel structure for the under frame [2-5]. Through the project, it was possible to confirm that the composite materials have potential to use as structural parts of railway vehicles. In addition, the composite material is possible to be applied for the energy absorption elements due to its high specific energy absorption capability. Various types of composite materials and structures, such as FRP tubes and sandwich panels have been tried in the effort to achieve improved level of crashworthiness [6-10]. In this study, the failure modes and energy absorption characterization of four different kinds of circular tubes made of carbon, glass, Kevlar and carbon-Kevlar hybrid fibres composites with epoxy resin have been evaluated. The materials used in this study have been or would be applied to train body structures in Korea.

2. Experimental

2.1 Material and specimens

These objectives of this study are to compare the energy absorption characteristics of circular tubes with different materials and different patterns such as unidirectional or woven fabric prepreg. In this study, four different kinds of circular tubes made of carbon, glass, Kevlar and carbon-Kevlar hybrid fibres composites with epoxy resin were used. These were fabricated by wrapping the prepreg material around a circular steel pipe using a table wrapper and overwrapped with a peel ply. The assembly was placed in an oven. These have nominally 100mm in length by 30mm inside diameter. Dimensions of the tubes were selected on the basis of stability and ease of fabrication. One end of each tube was chamfered with angle of 45 degrees to a trigger for the stable propagation of the collapse from that end. Figure 1 shows the typical circular tubes made of woven fabric.

Figure 1 Composite circular tubes fabricated with woven fabric.

The tubes were fabricated having ply orientation of $[90/0]_n$. The material types and patterns of the tubes are listed in Table 1. The tubes made of woven fabric have plain weave pattern except that Kevlar/epoxy has crowfoot weave pattern.

Table 1. Composite materials and types used to the compressive tests.

Materials	Stacking sequence	Pattern	Ply thickness(mm)	Designations
Glass/epoxy	$[90/0]_5$	UD	0.15	GL_U
	$[90/0]_4$	Plain weave	0.24	GL_F
Carbon/epoxy	$[90/0]_7$	UD	0.13	CA_U
	$[90/0]_4$	Plain weave	0.24	CA_F
Kevlar/epoxy	$[90/0]_{11}$	UD	0.1	KE_U
	$[90/0/90/0/90/0/90]_T$	Crowfoot weave	0.28	KE_F
Carbon-Kevlar/epoxy	$[90_C/0_K]_{11}$	UD	0.1	CK_U
	$[90_K/0_C]_{11}$	UD	0.1	KC_U
	$[90/0]_4$	Plain weave	0.34	CK_F

Table 2 lists the extensional modulus, interlaminar shear strength and fiber volume fraction. For the fabric material, the material properties of fill and warp direction were measured, respectively. In case of carbon-Kevlar hybrid material, carbon fiber was used in fill direction and Kevlar fiber in warp direction.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of each material.

Materials	E_1 (GPa)	ILSS(MPa)	Average Weight(g)	Volume fraction (%)
GL_U	39.2	66.1	34.8	50.1
GL_F	25.5(fill), 26.1(warp)	56.6(fill), 65.3(warp)	33.6	46.6
CA_U	130	71	28.3	67.3
CA_F	69.3(fill), 68.8(warp)	66.1(fill), 66.7(warp)	27.3	63.5
KE_U	83.9	63.2	23.8	-
KE_F	37.3(fill)	42.2(fill), 43.1(warp)	22.3	-
CK_U	105.2	70.1	24.9	-
KC_U	105.2	70.1	24.7	-
CK_F	65(fill), 33.2(warp)	54.4(fill), 49.4(warp)	23.2	-

2.2 Quasi-static compressive test procedures

Static crushing tests were performed in a 100kN capacity hydraulic loading machine. Load platens were set parallel to each other prior to initiation of the tests. All tubes were compressed 80~86mm at a rate of 10mm/min. Load and deflection of the cross-head were recorded by an automatic data acquisition system. Five replicate tests were carried out.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Load/displacement

The specific sustained crushing stress was used for comparing the energy absorption capability of the different tubes. The specific sustained crushing stress is the sustained crushing load divide by the product of the cross-sectional area and density [7]. It is independent of specimen cross-sectional area, material density and the amount of the tube crushed. Therefore, it was used in this study for energy absorption comparison. Figure 2 shows the load-displacement curve of different tubes made of unidirectional tape. From Figure 2, the carbon/epoxy tube had highest peak and mean load whereas Kevlar/epoxy tube was lowest peak and mean load. Glass/epoxy tube was crushed with almost ideal load-displacement curve. The load-displacement curve of tubes including Kevlar as reinforced fiber presented non-uniform load history and low mean crushing load compared with glass and carbon fiber.

Figure 2 Load-displacement curves of different tubes made of unidirectional tape.

Figure 3 shows the load-displacement curve of different tubes made of woven fabric tape. From Figure 3, the carbon/epoxy tube had highest peak and mean load whereas carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tube was lowest peak and mean load. The load-displacement curve of tubes made of woven fabric tape showed more uniform behaviour after initial peak load than the tubes with unidirectional fiber.

Figure 3 Load-displacement curves of different tubes made of woven fabric tape.

Table 3 lists the all of the test results for maximum peak load, mean load and specific sustain stress. Unidirectional carbon/epoxy tube has highest peak load, however, woven fabric carbon/epoxy tube shows better energy absorption capability. Woven fabric carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tube showed the lowest peak and means load whereas

unidirectional Kevlar/epoxy tube has worst energy absorption capability. The woven fabric carbon/epoxy tube has almost two times energy absorption capability than the unidirectional Kevlar/epoxy tube.

Table 3 Summary of the crush test results.

Material	Peak load(kN)	Mean load(kN)	Specific Sustaining stress(Nm/kg)
GL_U	25.5	22.4	64.6
GL_F	25.5	23.1	68.9
CA_U	31.3	25.2	89.2
CA_F	31.1	26.6	98.1
KE_U	17.6	12.8	54.0
KE_F	19.1	15.8	71.1
CK_U	26.8	17.8	71.9
KC_U	23.3	18.9	77.1
CK_F	17.0	12.6	54.5

Table 4 Crushing sequences of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy tube.

Crushed length	0mm	20mm	40mm
Crushed shape			
Crushed length	60mm	80mm	Final
Crushed shape			

3.2 Crush process

The composite tubes with unidirectional and woven fabric glass and unidirectional carbon showed a typical brittle fracturing mode which is a combination of the transverse shearing and lamina bending crushing modes. The transverse shearing crushing mode is characterized by a wedge-shaped laminate cross section with one or multiple short interlaminar and longitudinal cracks which form partial lamina bundles. Two crushing mechanisms control the crushing process for the transverse shearing crushing mode; interlaminar crack growth and lamina bundle fracture. The lamina bending crushing mode is characterized by very long interlaminar, intralaminar, and parallel-to-fiber cracks, but the lamina bundles do not fracture. Whereas the interlaminar cracks form and grow at the interface of adjacent layers, the intralaminar cracks form and grow within individual layers. The parallel-to-fiber cracks propagate parallel to the fiber direction within a ply or within several adjacent lamina that have common fiber orientations. Two mechanisms control the crushing process in the lamina bending crushing mode. These mechanisms are inter/intralaminar and parallel-to-fiber crack growth and friction. During crushing process of these tubes, lamina bundles were bended inward and outward of tubes and fractured as shown in Table 4.

Figure 4 Glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy tubes after crush tests.

Figure 4 presented the final shape of glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy tubes after tests. As shown in Figure 4, lamina bundles formed from tube wall of both glass/epoxy tubes and unidirectional carbon/epoxy tube curled inward and outward of tubes and there is a lot of debris of these bundles fractured while crushing. In case of woven fabric carbon/epoxy tube, however, it cannot be found any debris and the lamina bundles were bended without fracture. The composite tubes with unidirectional and woven fabric Kevlar and unidirectional carbon-Kevlar/epoxy showed a typical local buckling crushing mode. The crushing mode consists of the formation of local buckles by means

of plastic deformation of the fiber/matrix material. In case of these tubes, as shown in Figure 5, there was no formation of laminar bundles along the circumference of the tube wall, but unidirectional Kevlar-carbon/epoxy and woven fabric carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tube showed the lamina bending crushing mode without fracture.

Table 4 Crushing sequences of a woven fabric carbon/epoxy tube.

Crushed length	0mm	20mm	40mm
Crushed shape			
Crushed length	60mm	80mm	Final
Crushed shape			

(a) Unidirectional Kevlar/epoxy tube

(b) Woven fabric Kevlar/epoxy tube

(c) UD carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tube

(d) UD Kevlar-carbon/epoxy tube

(e) Woven fabric carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tube

Figure 5 Kevlar/epoxy and carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tubes after crush tests.

The energy absorption capability is one of the requirements for crashworthy structures. Post crushing structural integrity is also important because the structure must remain intact to provide protection for the occupants. Based on the tests, as mentioned previous researches, Kevlar/epoxy tubes were showed good post crushing structural integrity

whereas glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy tubes were bad. For the unidirectional carbon-Kevlar hybrid tubes, [90_C/0_K] tubes showed good structural integrity like Kevlar/epoxy tubes but [90_C/0_K] tubes were crushed like the tubes made of brittle fibers.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the failure modes and energy absorption characterization of four different kinds of circular tubes made of carbon, glass, Kevlar and carbon-Kevlar hybrid fibres composites with epoxy resin have been evaluated. The materials used in this study have been or would be applied to train body structures in Korea. These tubes were fabricated with unidirectional and woven fabric tape. The woven fabric carbon/epoxy tubes absorbed more energy than others.

In case of the tubes fabricated by unidirectional tape, the carbon/epoxy tube had highest peak and mean load whereas Kevlar/epoxy tube was lowest peak and mean load. The load-displacement curve of tubes including Kevlar as reinforced fiber presented non-uniform load history and low mean crushing load compared with glass and carbon fiber. [90_K/0_C] tubes failed in a local buckling mode and showed good post crushing integrity whereas [90_C/0_K] tubes failed in a lamina bending mode and bad post crushing integrity

Woven fabric carbon/epoxy tube shows better energy absorption capability. Woven fabric carbon-Kevlar/epoxy tube showed the lowest peak and means load whereas unidirectional Kevlar/epoxy tube has worst energy absorption capability.

References

1. Wennhage P. Structural-acoustic Optimization of Sandwich Panels, 2001, Report 2001-05.
2. Kim J. S., Lee S. J. and Shin K. B., "Manufacturing and Structural Safety Evaluation of a Composite Train Carbody," *Composite Structures*, , Vol. 78, pp. 468–476, 2007.
3. Kim J. S. and Cheong S. K., "A Study on the Low Velocity Impact Response of Laminates for Composite Railway Bodyshells," *Composite Structures*, Vol. 77, pp. 484–492, 2007.
4. Kim J. S. and Cheong J. C., "Natural Frequency Evaluation of a composite Train Carbody with Length of 23m," *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 66, pp. 2272-2283, 2006.
5. Kim J. S., Cheong J. C. and Lee S. J., "Numerical and Experimental Studies on the Deformational Behavior of a Composite Train Carbody of the Korean Tilting Train," *Composite Structures*, Vol. 81, pp. 225-241, 2008.
6. Thornton, P. H. and Edwards, P. J. "Energy Absorption in Composite Tubes," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 16, November, pp. 521-544, 1982.
7. Farley, Gary L. "Energy Absorption of Composite Materials," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 17, May, pp. 267-279, 1983.

8. Farley, Gary L. "Effect of Fiber and Matrix Maximum Strain on the Energy Absorption of Composite Materials," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 20, July, pp. 322-334, 1986.
9. Farley, Gary L., Bird, Richard K., and Modlin, John T. "The Role of Fiber and Matrix in Crash Energy Absorption of Composite Materials," *Journal of the American Helicopter Society*, April, pp. 52-58, 1989.
10. Farley, Gary L and Jones, Robert M. "Crushing Characteristics of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Composite Tubes," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 1, 1992, pp. 37-50.